

Supporting information

Hydrothermal and co-precipitation combined with photo-reduced preparation of Ag/AgBr/MgBi₂O₆ composites for the visible-light degradation toward organics

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Figure S1. SEM image of MgBi₂O₆ and EDS-mapping of Mg, Bi, and O elements.

Figure S2. SEM image of AgBr/MgBi₂O₆ composites and EDS-mapping of Mg, Bi, and O elements

Figure S3. SEM images of Ag/AgBr/MgBi₂O₆ composites and EDS-mapping of Mg, Bi, and O elements

Figure S4. XPS analysis of MgBi₂O₆: full scan and high resolution of XPS for Mg, Bi, and O elements.

Figure S5. XPS analysis of AgBr/MgBi₂O₆ composites: full scan and high resolution of XPS for Ag, Br, Mg, Bi, and O elements.

Figure S6. XPS analysis of Ag/AgBr/MgBi₂O₆ composites: full scan, and high resolution of XPS for Ag, Br, Mg, Bi, and O elements.

Figure S7. Optimum conditions of Ag/AgBr/MgBi₂O₆ composites: (A) different synthesis steps, (B) different light source irradiation, (C) different concentrations of AgNO₃, and (D) different irradiation times.